

UDC 544

DETERMINATION OF RADIONUCLIDES AND INORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN SOIL SAMPLES

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Abstract: Radionuclides and inorganic compounds in soil samples taken from north-west areas of country were determined. Research of radionuclides in the samples were determined using a high-purity germanium (HPGe) detector, while the mineralogy was analyzed through X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) methods. The level of soil contamination and the analysis of potential ecological risks were evaluated in terms of the natural background radioactivity in the area and its ecological and agricultural impacts. The concentrations of sulfates and chlorides of elements such as Na, K, Ca, Sr, Fe, Mn, Zn, and others were determined. Overall, the research findings showed that the activity of radionuclides in the soil samples were relatively low. The activity of natural isotopes ^{65}Zn , ^{91}Sr , ^{113}Sn , ^{126}Sn and ^{228}Th in taken soil samples is within the natural background range.

Keywords: radioactivity background, soil, soil contamination, radionuclides.

INTRODUCTION

The north-west areas of Azerbaijan an area with diverse geological and soil structures. Study of the radionuclide composition and mineralogy of the soil in the area is important in terms of understanding the ecological state, agricultural potential and geological processes of the region. Assessment of the resistance of soil ecosystems to radioactive contamination is of great importance in terms of environmental safety [1-3]. Therefore, the determination of radionuclides and minerals in soil is important for both environmental protection and the safety of agricultural activities [4-6]. The aim of this study is to determine the content of radionuclides and major minerals in soil samples in the north-west territory of country, to assess their sources and possible ecological impacts.

METHODOLOGICAL PART

Soil samples for the research were taken from three different parts of north-west areas of country, namely, the agricultural zone, the natural landscape zone and the residential zone. Soil samples were dug up to a depth of 20 cm from the top layer of the soil and dried by the laboratory, sieved through a 2 mm sieve and homogenized. They were divided into parts weighing up to 200 g. The selected sample was extracted from the soil after radiometric measurements, classified according to the physicochemical parameters of the separated mineral and studied by analytical-chemical research methods of laboratories, X-ray fluorescence, gamma and atomic absorption spectroscopy, electron microscopy [2-4].

Radiomonitoring and radiometric measurements were carried out with the “InSpector 1000” (“Canberra” Co., USA-France) radiometer-dosimeter, the “Radiagem 2000” (“Canberra” Co., USA-France) radiometer-counters for alpha, beta, gamma, neutron radiation, and the “IdentiFINDER” (Thermo Scientific Co., AFR-USA) radiometer identifier.

Radionuclide analysis was carried out by determining the activity of radionuclides in soil samples using gamma-ray spectrometry. The presence, quality and quantitative composition of major minerals (quartz, feldspars, clays, etc.) were determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) and infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The concentration of heavy metals and other chemical elements in the soil was assessed using atomic emission spectroscopy and X-ray fluorescence analysis (XRF).

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS.

The concentration of macroelements and microelements in the soil sample, that is, as a result of soil monitoring, is established in Tables 1 and 2.

Based on the measurement results, we can say that 30-35% (300-350 g/kg) of a dry soil sample consists of water. The oxygen content of dried soil samples is 240-260 g/kg, in wet soil this figure is approximately 50% or 500 g/kg, the carbon content is 18-20 g/kg, the silicon content is 310-330 g/kg, and the aluminum content is 62-80 g/kg, i.e. the total amount of moisture, oxygen, carbon, silicon, and aluminum is 980 - 990 g/kg (350 + 240 + 18 + 310 + 62 = 980 g. or 300 + 260 + 20 + 330 + 80 = 990 g). In soil samples, Mg element compounds are observed at a concentration of 80-90 mg/kg, and the concentrations of As, Sn, Cu, Cr, Ti, Zr, Mo, Br, and Ba microelements are less than 1 mg/kg. As can be seen from Table 1, the total amount of microelements that determine soil fertility is only 10-20 g/kg, and the results of measuring total radioactive radiation, assessing types of radioactive radiation, and studying the distribution of radionuclides in the soil in the regions of the country are given [2-4].

Table 1.

Concentration of components in soil samples taken from north-west areas of country.

Soil samples taken from north-west areas of country	Components, mg/kg								
	Sulfates	Chlorides	Na; K	Ca/all carbonates	Sr	NO ₃ ; NO ₂	Fe; Mn	Zn	As
	500	130	184; 6410	5316	40	75; 1.7	94; 18	1.0	0

The results of radiometric measurements and radionuclide activity in soil samples taken from areas and pastures with similar green cover in the country's regions are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Results of radiometric measurements and radionuclide activity in soil samples taken from green plains and pastures in the territory of north-west areas of country.

Soil samples taken from north-west areas of country (background, 0.03 μSv / h; alpha radiation, 0 Bq / cm ²)	Isotopes, Bq/kg					
	¹¹ Na ²²	¹⁹ K ⁴⁰	³⁰ Zn ⁶⁵	³⁸ Sr ⁹¹	⁵⁰ Sn ¹¹³ , ⁵⁰ Sn ¹²⁶	⁹⁰ Th ²²⁸
	1,5	2.0	0,16	0,50	0,02; 0,02	0,05

Figure 1. Activity of the $^{38}\text{Sr}^{91}$ radioisotope in the extracts and soil residues separated after washing 200 gram soil samples taken from north-west areas of country with solutions of various amounts of nitric acid in 1, 2 and 3 liters of distilled water.

Figure 2. Activity of $^{38}\text{Sr}^{91}$ radioisotope in the separated extracts and soil residues after washing soil samples weighing 200 grams taken from north-west territory of country with different amounts of sodium hydroxide solutions in 1, 2 and 3 liters of distilled water.

Figure 3. Activity of the $^{38}\text{Sr}^{91}$ radioisotope in the extracts and soil residues separated after washing 200 gram soil samples taken from north-west areas of country with solutions of various amounts of nitric and hydrochloric acid in 1, 2 and 3 liters of distilled water.

It was observed that radionuclides in soil samples corresponded to the natural background level. However, the relatively high concentration of radionuclides ($\text{K}40$, $\text{Na}40$, $^{30}\text{Zn}^{65}$, $^{38}\text{Sr}^{91}$, $^{50}\text{Sn}^{113}$, $^{50}\text{Sn}^{126}$ and $^{90}\text{Th}^{228}$) in some samples in certain regions can be explained by the characteristics of north-west areas, which is rich in clay and silicate rocks.

These are mineral components such as quartz, feldspars, carbonate and mineral substances that can be used. In some samples, high levels of clay minerals affect the water retention properties of the soil [1, 5]. Sulfates and chlorides were found in higher concentrations in some soil samples [4-6].

According to the results, the soils in the territory of north-west areas of country are generally stable in terms of ecological safety. The level of radionuclides in the soil is determined by directive indicators.

CONCLUSION

Radionuclide and mineral composition analyses conducted in the soils of samples taken from north-west areas of country have allowed us to determine the main indicators of soil quality in these areas. The results show that there is no ecological contamination with nuclear materials. Radionuclide contamination of the soil in north-west areas of country is at the natural background level and does not pose a serious threat to the environment. At the same time, it is advisable to conduct long-term observations and monitor possible anthropogenic impacts.

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